

**THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF PRESCHOOL
CHILDREN**

Mirzajonova Munavvar Muzaffar qizi,

Sadullayeva Asal Rustam qizi

Scientific adviser: PhD, associate professor **Yusupova Mukhabbat Anatolevna**

Chirchik State Pedagogical University Faculty: Tourism

Phone numbers: 935234504 931360445

mirzajonova.04@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

The article considers the conceptual sphere of the problem, the main components of a senior preschool child's sociocultural development in the process of learning the culture of world nations. It distinguishes cognitive, emotional, communicative and creative components of the sociocultural learning. The authors have developed a program on British culture learning designed to expand children's ideas about diversity of world cultures, to develop motivation for foreign language study, and to provide certain sociocultural basics.

Key words: sociocultural development, senior preschool age child, culture, social development.

INTRODUCTION

The modern educational situation is focused on developing the younger generation's readiness for multifaceted interaction and partnership in different sociocultural conditions. However, an active life position is impossible without knowledge of the cultural traditions of one's own and other peoples.

In preschool age, the formation of basic personality characteristics occurs: self-esteem, emotional-need sphere, moral values and attitudes, as well as socio-psychological characteristics in communicating with people. All this actualizes the problem of sociocultural education of children at the socio-pedagogical level.

The federal state standard for preschool education defines the task of introducing children to sociocultural norms, traditions of the family, society and state; emphasizes the

need to form in children primary ideas about cultural traditions, about the diversity of cultures of countries and peoples of the world, as a result of which the socio-cultural development of the child is carried out.

According to O.V. Fedoskina, the sociocultural development of a person is carried out in the process of entering the context of modern culture, appropriating universal and domestic values, social norms and traditions. At the same time, one builds one's life trajectory, gains experience and free self-determination.¹

K.I. Chizhova studied the characteristics of the sociocultural development of preschool children in musical activity. She notes that immersion in active musical creative activity creates fertile conditions for mastering cultural universal values and entering society.²

Sociocultural development is a specific concept of the socialization process highlighting culture (social, individual) as a determining factor in personal development.

In the culture of a particular society, it is possible to identify its substantive components, which provide a generalized schematic representation of the most value vectors of its functioning and development. In our opinion, these include such elements as geographical, civil, linguistic and ethnic culture. The identified components can be considered both as part of the culture of society, and as components of personal culture, characterizing the level of its development.

The language of society and the language of an individual are reflections of culture and are considered indicators of its level in any nation. Linguistic culture forms the general culture of any society and individual and contributes to their development.

When considering the process of introducing children to the culture of the peoples of the world, it is important to determine the content accessible to a preschool child. Knowledge of a geographical nature presupposes that children become familiar with the peculiarities of the climate determined by the location of a particular state with ecological monuments the civil legal component guides teachers towards developing children's ideas about state symbols and architectural objects of global significance the ethnocultural

¹ Fedoskina O.V. Pedagogical means of sociocultural development of junior schoolchildren in the educational process: dis. ...cand. ped. Sci. M., 2004. 245 p.

² Chizhova K.I. Sociocultural development of children in the process of musical education: dis. ...cand. ped. Sci. M., 2002. 147 p.

orientation of education introduces the child to the world of folk art, holidays, traditions, customs.

The linguistic component involves familiarity with a foreign language and mastery of certain forms of verbal communication. The sociocultural development of a preschooler in the process of familiarization with the culture of the peoples of the world is characterized by changes in all spheres of personality. In this regard, the main components of the sociocultural development of children in the process of learning the culture of the peoples of the world are:

- cognitive-normative (ideas about the culture of one's country; the culture of other peoples, countries; knowledge in the field of norms of behavior, communication in accordance with the culture of society (general and specific));
- emotional and value-based;
- communicative and creative (compliance with the rules of interaction in everyday communication, mastery of means of communication; knowledge of a foreign language in accordance with age and educational objectives); creative application of the cognizable in productive activity.

As evidenced by the results of the ascertaining stage, the sociocultural development of children aged 6-7 years in the process of familiarization with the culture of the peoples of the world is characterized by the fact that it is mainly carried out spontaneously - children receive information from external sources. At the same time, the teacher, relying on the child's interest and existing experience, can become a partner for the subsequent training of preschoolers in the dialogue of cultures.

To expand children's ideas about the culture of the peoples of the world, develop interest in their diversity, and form a value-based attitude towards folk traditions, we have developed a program to familiarize themselves with the culture of the English people, which provides for expanding children's ideas about the diversity of world cultures, developing positive motivation for learning a foreign language, mastering a certain sociocultural minimum that allows one to expand speech and regional knowledge about England and cultivate a friendly attitude towards people of other nationalities.

The main approaches that underlie the development of this program: cultural, communicative, systemic, activity-based and environmental. They make it possible to take into account both the age characteristics of children and the main factors of personal

development. Responses to the first group of research tasks indicate that the main hypothesis was confirmed that the organization of educational activities and the implementation of educational tasks in preschool institution are largely more effective with the help of computer technology.

The disproportion of the results suggests that preschool educators acquired most of their digital skills and competences through various forms of informal education on their own. Finally, the fourth specific hypothesis has not been confirmed as well. The responses argue that the working conditions and the technical resources of the surveyed institutions are insufficient for the successful implementation of computer technology and the delivery of the planned activities.

REFERENCES:

1. Bolshunova N.Ya. Sociocultural development of children with disabilities as the main path to their rehabilitation. 11P1_: <http://lib.convdocs.org/docs/index-196048.html> (access date: 11/11/2013).
2. Fedoskina O.V. Pedagogical means of sociocultural development of junior schoolchildren in the educational process: dis. ...cand. ped. Sci. M., 2004. 245 p.
3. Chizhova K.I. Sociocultural development of children in the process of musical education: dis. ...cand. ped. Sci. M., 2002. 147 p.
4. Kemerov V. Philosophical Encyclopedia. M., 1998.
5. Gurevich P. Dictionary of cultural studies. M., 1996.
6. Shabatura L.N. Tradition in the sociocultural development of personality: dis. ... Doctor of Philosophy Sci. M., 2004. 414 p.
7. Akhiezer A. Sociocultural dictionary. 11P1_: http://royallib.ru/book/ahiezer_a/sotsiokulturniy_slovar.html (accessed date: 11/11/2013).
8. Khalupo O.I. Language culture and linguocultural competence // Bulletin of Chelyabinsk